

CHEMICAL ASPECTS OF NITROGEN FIXATION IN SOILS AND CROP PRODUCTION*

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I am very grateful to the Council of the Indian Chemical Society, and specially Prof. P. Rây, for inviting me to deliver the first lecture in commemoration of our great Guru, Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray. I had the good fortune to be closely associated with him since 1907 till his death in 1944. I was initiated by him in 1911 in investigations on the physical properties of nitrites and hyponitrites, and we published a series of joint papers on this line in the Journal of the English Chemical Society. These investigations have now formed a part of the literature in Physical and Inorganic Chemistry. My Guru had the impression that electric conductivity and other physical properties could not be determined in India at that time and it would be necessary for him to go to England to obtain the "Conductivity" water needed for these experiments. A little later, with the help of my friends, Shri D. N. Bhattacharya, Shri A. K. Dutta and others, we determined the transport number of the nitrite ion by the electrolysis of silver nitrite solutions at different concentrations, dissociation constant of nitrous acid and the kinetics of the reaction between iodine and nitrite, both in light and in the dark, and the action of nitric acid on mercury, copper, zinc and several reducing agents. Hence, I followed the footsteps of my Guru in the study of nitrite chemistry.

For over 25 years we have investigated the problem of nitrogen fixation and nitrogen loss with a band of able young men in the Chemical Laboratories of the University of Allahabad and the Sheila Dhar Institute of Soil Science with the ultimate view to ease the world food situation by increasing land fertility as cheaply as possible. Our Guru used to say that "*Anna Chinta Chamatkara*" "अन्नचिन्ता चमत्कारा", supply of food is the real problem of our country.

In this connection it will be of great interest to record here the remarks of the late Prof. H. E. Armstrong in his article on 'Future of Chemistry in India' in the Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray Memorial Volume (1932, pp. 15-16).

"The great work of the future, however, specially in India, will be the development of agriculture with the definite object in view of providing food of approved value, far higher in quality than that now produced. Only in recent years have we been able to set this before us as our object."

"We have failed thus far, even in England, to place Agriculture upon a pedestal of the highest scientific endeavour. We have had no efficient College to this end. I can imagine no higher service to India than the establishment of such an institution. Only a potential Liebig will be able to bring it into being and supervise its operations.

*First Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray Memorial Lecture, delivered on August 2, 1948 in Calcutta.

Twenty years hence, perhaps, such a leader may be forthcoming, if meanwhile a few men who feel that they have some call to such service, some biological feeling, will set themselves in training, disregarding academic traditions and forswearing all desire to advertise that they have knocked another spot off another atom or in some other way, of remote concern to the world, made themselves exceptional."

"Competent chemists, they will carry on their studies, both in field and laboratory, in every possible and desirable direction, so as to secure a commanding knowledge of the problems of animal and plant life and of the soil. Only men so qualified, with ripened powers of imagination, will be competent to act as saviours of the people in the not distant future. The example Sir Prafulla Chandra Ray has set may well serve to encourage such an order into being. They will be the scientific missionaries of the future, sworn to social service alone."

Although organic matter has been used as a manure from times immemorial, and even today 97% of world food production has to be attributed to the humus of the soil—3% being due to the application of artificial nitrogen—the functions of organic matter in the soil have not been properly cleared up.

FIXATION OF ATMOSPHERIC NITROGEN IN SOIL BY ADDING ORGANIC MATTER

About 25 years ago over 100 sugar factories were newly started in India and 100,000 tons of molasses, which is a by-product of the industry, were practically wasted. We started a large number of experiments on the use of molasses as a manure for normal and alkaline soils. From our experiments, which are reproducible under European conditions with a different time factor, we concluded that there was considerable nitrogen increase when molasses was mixed with soil or sand and allowed to undergo slow oxidation in air, both in sterile and unsterile conditions. In every case the initial, total and available nitrogen of the mixture were determined and it was observed that after 3 or 4 weeks, the ammoniacal and total nitrogen increased markedly and the carbon of the system decreased. We also observed that increase of nitrogen (total and ammoniacal) was more pronounced when the system received sunlight or artificial light than when kept in dark. From these experiments we came to the conclusion that molasses, when added to soil or sand, fixed atmospheric nitrogen more in light than in dark. Nitrogen fixation is much greater in sand in which the initial nitrogen is lower than in soil.

As molasses cannot be obtained in other countries for manuring fields, we carried on experiments with other energy-producing materials like sugars, fats, oils, straw, leaves, paper, cowdung, lignin, sawdust, lignite and coals. In the case of molasses, sugars, glycerol and other readily-soluble energy materials, oxidation of carbonaceous substances and nitrogen fixation are more rapid than with other types of energy materials, and the total and ammoniacal nitrogen go on increasing from the very beginning; but with the other group of energy-producing materials, the increase of total nitrogen (and not ammoniacal nitrogen) takes place up to 4 or 6 months. After this period there is an increase of ammoniacal nitrogen also in the system. A few of our experimental results with straw, cowdung and coal are recorded below.

TABLE I

Experiments with straw.

100 g. of soil + 3.75 g. of wheat straw.

Date.	Total C in 100 g. soil.	Total N in 100 g. soil.	*Efficiency.
Unsterile (exposed to sunlight).			
28-6-47	1.886 g.	0.0622 g.	...
6-1-48	1.571	0.0698	24.8
18-3-48	1.442	0.0730	24.6
28-6-48	1.281	0.0765	24.6
Covered (dark).			
28-6-47	1.886	0.0622	...
6-1-48	1.735	0.0639	11.2
18-3-48	1.563	0.0647	11.1
28-5-48	1.569	0.0657	10.6
100 g. of soil + 2.5 g. of wheat straw.			
Unsterile (exposed to sunlight).			
28-6-47	1.386	0.0544	...
6-1-48	1.091	0.0619	25.4
18-3-48	0.975	0.0648	25.0
28-6-48	0.851	0.0678	24.0
Covered.			
28-6-47	1.386	0.0544	...
6-1-48	1.243	0.0662	12.4
18-3-48	1.181	0.0569	11.3
28-6-48	1.100	0.0578	11.0

*Nitrogen fixed in mg. /g. of carbon oxidised.

TABLE II

Experiments with cowdung.

250 g. of soil + 40 g. of cowdung.

Date.	Total C in 100 g. soil.	Total N in 100 g. soil	†Azotobacter count.	*Efficiency.
Unsterile (light).				
3-1-47	1.476 g.	0.0931 g.	2.5	...
5-3-47	1.212	0.0996	18.0	21.0
3-5-47	1.001	0.1029	39.0	20.0
Unsterile (dark).				
5-1-47	1.460	0.0924	2.5	...
7-3-47	1.310	0.0942	72.0	11.8
5-5-47	1.181	0.0955	135.0	10.0
Sterile (light).				
8-1-47	1.442	0.0916	...	...
10-3-47	1.277	0.0941	...	15.4
9-5-47	1.139	0.0962	...	15.0
Sterile (dark).				
10-1-47	1.460	0.0924	...	...
11-5-47	1.285	0.0939	...	8.2

†In million per g. of dry soil.

*N fixed in mg./g. of carbon oxidised.

TABLE III

Experiments with coal.

The mixture was exposed to sunlight in dishes from April 10 to August 10, 1950 and then analysed. It was daily stirred and kept moist with distilled water.

		State.	C initially present in 100 g. of sand.	C oxidised in 100 g. of sand after exposure for 250 hrs. (April 10 to Aug. 10).	Total N initially present in 100 g. of sand.	Gain in total N per 100 g. of sand after exposure.	Efficiency.
C-sterile.							
Sand+ Indian lignite	250 g. 2%	Exposed.	1.2732 ^g	0.1922 g.	15.26 mg.	4.28 mg.	22.26
		Covered.	1.2732	0.1300	15.26	1.29	9.91
Sand+ Indian lignite	250 g. 1%	Exposed.	0.6366	0.0951	7.63	1.999	21.02
		Covered.	0.6366	0.0616	7.63	1.827	13.42
Sand+ Indian lignite +wheat straw	250 g. 2% 2%	Exposed.	2.0461	0.4819	28.46	9.51	19.03
		Covered.	2.0461	0.4509	28.46	4.49	9.95
Sand+ Indian lignite +wheat straw	250 g. 1% 2%	Exposed.	1.4096	0.3995	20.85	7.96	19.91
		Covered.	1.4096	0.3766	20.85	4.35	10.75
Sand+ Assam coal	250 g. 2%	Exposed.	1.5756	0.0662	26.40	1.03	15.55.
		Covered.	1.5756	0.0226	26.40	0.79	8.40
Sand+ Assam coal	250 g. 1%	Exposed.	0.7878	0.0321	13.20	0.49	15.26
		Covered.	0.7878	0.0178	13.20	0.13	7.30
Sand+ Assam coal +wheat straw	250 g. 2% 2%	Exposed.	2.3485	0.0185	39.62	7.32	17.49
		Covered.	2.3485	0.3860	39.62	4.19	10.85
Sand+ Assam coal +wheat straw	250 g. 1% 2%	Exposed.	1.5608	0.3753	26.42	7.67	20.44
		Covered.	1.5608	0.3558	26.42	4.21	11.83

Moreover, by adding repeated doses of municipal rubbish with a C/N ratio much greater than 10 to our soils containing 0.04% total nitrogen, the nitrogen status has been raised to 0.25% and bumper crops have been obtained in these improved lands.

In the Presidential Address to the National Academy of Sciences, India, on 19th December 1935, I concluded from a large amount of experimental observations that the chief function of organic matter added to the soil was fixation of nitrogen. In numerous subsequent publications I have developed the same theme from experiments with all types of energy materials including coals. I have also emphasised that a mixture of organic substance with artificial nitrogenous matter is a better manure than ammonium salts alone. Some of our results are recorded below.

TABLE IV

Amount of nitrogen fixed in light per g. of carbon oxidised.

	Sterile.				Unsterile.			
	Original N in the system in per cent.				Original N in the system in per cent.			
	0.	0.001.	0.05.	0.08.	0.	0.001.	0.05.	0.08.
Glucose	38	28	13	9	40	29	14	10
Cane sugar	38	27	12	8	39	28	14	10
Mannitol	37	28	12	8	40	28	13	9
Starch	40	28	13	9	40	29	14	10
Glycerol	39	28	12	9	38	28	13	9
Butter	38	28	11	8	39	29	13	9
Cellulose	40	30	14	10	41	30	13	10
Lignin	34	26	11	7	33	25	12	...
Coal	25	20	...	...	26	21	...	...

In the absence of light the fixation of nitrogen is less than half of that in light. In the system with no initial nitrogen, pure oxides of iron, zinc, manganese, nickel, aluminium etc. were used instead of soil. In these experiments either there was no phosphate present in the system or the percentage of P_2O_5 did not exceed 0.075, *i. e.* the phosphate status was low.

On obtaining these results we consulted the literature on the subject and found that on adding farmyard manure to Rothamsted soil, marked increase of nitrogen was reported, and hence, in my Address, referred to above, I stated as follows:

"Russell ("Soil Conditions & Plant Growth", 1932, pp. 76-78, 313, 361) has reported that the yield of barley and straw with farmyard manure in Rothamsted field experiments from 1852-1922 is better than that obtained with complete artificial manures containing ammonium salts, potassium salts and phosphates. This is due to the fact that there is more nitrogen in the field manured with cowdung than with artificials, as is evident from the following data from the Rothamsted fields:

	Total N%
(1) Receiving no manure since 1843	... 0.095
(2) Receiving farmyard manure since 1852	... 0.256
(3) Receiving complete artificials & $(NH_4)_2SO_4$	... 0.09
(4) Receiving potash & phosphate but no nitrogen	... 0.090

After a few years I learnt that marked increase of soil nitrogen had also been reported in the Missouri Experiment Station by the use of barnyard manure. Similarly in Lyngby (Denmark) the following results were obtained.

TABLE V

% Nitrogen in air-dry soil.

	Unmanured.	Farmyard manure.	% Nitrogen increase.
Askov loam-field 1942	0.106	0.130	22.6
Askov sand-field 1942	0.066	0.086	30
Lyngby 1933	0.146	0.169	15.7

Moreover, E. M. Crowther, in his paper on "The Study of Soil Organic Matter & Organic Manures by means of Field Experiments" has recorded the following results:

TABLE VI

*Nitrogen contents of Brodbalk soils, Rothamsted (metric tons per ha.).
Gain over unmanured plot in relation to amount of nitrogen previously added
as farmyard manure.*

	Plot 2 B.			"Original N in 1843: 0.122%".				Plot 2 A.	
	Gain.	Added.	Gain as % of added.	Gain.	Added.	Gain as % of added.	Gain.	Added.	Gain as % of added.
1865	1.8	4.9	37	...	...	...	...	...	...
1881	2.1	8.5	25	...	...	...	...	...	...
1893	3.0	11.2	27	1893	1.0	2.0	50		
1914	4.0	15.9	25	1914	2.5	6.7	37		
1936	3.1	20.2	15	1936	2.1	10.7	20		
1945	3.3	22.4	15	1945	2.2	12.9	17		

From Crowther's paper it will be seen that the gain in total nitrogen in the Rothamsted plots has been more marked in the beginning of the experiments than in later periods. This cannot be attributed, as is generally done, only to the retention of the nitrogen added in the form of farmyard manure. The original soil nitrogen in Rothamsted was 0.122% in 1843 when manuring experiments were first started. In the first 22 years there was more marked increase of soil nitrogen (46%) than in the next 28 years (21%). If the retention of the added nitrogen were the cause of the increase of total nitrogen observed, this behaviour should have been more marked in the later period of the experiments when the total nitrogen content of the soil became high. It is well known that when organic matter is added to the soil of low humus content, the added organic matter is oxidised very rapidly in the beginning. Hence, our conclusion that cowdung or farmyard manure not only supplies the nitrogen it contains but it also fixes atmospheric nitrogen by utilising the energy obtained from the oxidation of carbohydrates, pentosans and other compounds present in farmyard manure, can explain the Rothamsted, Missouri and Lyngby results where more marked nitrogen increase has been reported in soils containing smaller amounts of total nitrogen.

HUMUS NITROGEN DUE CHIEFLY TO NITROGEN FIXATION

It is estimated that 35 billion kilograms, *i. e.* 34750 million tons of cellulose containing 13750 million tons of carbon are added every year to the earth. From our experiments we find that 40% of the carbon is oxidised in our climatic conditions in 4 or 5 months, and even if the same amount be taken to be oxidised on the surface of the whole earth in one year, it would mean that 5500 million tons of carbon are oxidised every year. On a moderate estimate of 15 mg. nitrogen fixation per gram of carbon oxidised in sunlight, about 82.5 million metric tons of nitrogen are added to the earth by fixation provided that 40% of the carbon added is oxidised. We can conclude that out of the total 82.5 million tons, at least 50%, *i. e.* 41.25 million tons of nitrogen are fixed in soils by absorption of solar light. The total output of nitrogen fixed synthetically in the factories of the world in 1937 was 3.54 million tons, *i. e.* 1/12 th of what is obtained by fixation under natural conditions by the utilisation of sunlight.